

Springboks, Spitfire bows and family archery – the National Museum Bloemfontein’s Du Plessis Collection and its national and international intersections

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ABSTRACT

Despite being an integral part of the country’s sporting identity, the history of competitive archery remains a neglected area of South Africa’s sports history. Following its establishment in the 1860s as an elitist recreational activity characterised by social gatherings and merrymaking, it gradually developed into a well-organised and nationally coordinated sport during the 20th century. En route, it intersected with issues such as race, gender, professionalism, and politics, all of which collectively shaped its South African character. Due to a lack of original archives, none of the affiliated members of Archery South Africa have thus far documented their own illustrious past. This article, using the literature on artefact biographies, reconstructs the history of both South African and Free State archery with the aid of a small number of artefacts in the collection of the National Museum, Bloemfontein.

KEYWORDS: Apartheid, archery, Bloemfontein, Du Plessis, museum, Orange Free State, South Africa, sport

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INTRODUCTION

Included in the History Collection of the National Museum, Bloemfontein, are three trophies, all awarded for achievements in archery, and a beautifully made Grove’s ‘Spitfire’ bow (Fig. 1).¹ In addition, the collection includes a scrapbook, various newspaper cuttings, events programmes and tickets, photographs, private correspondence, three trophies, and other ephemera. The bow, the Groves Spitfire 42TH, is a recurve bow that was manufactured by American bowmaker, Harold Groves at the end of the 1950s and imported into South Africa. Groves’ products were traditionally manufactured from risers of rosewood, zebrawood, ebony, and various colours of fiberglass. Due to the Groves bow’s flexibility and ease of handling, over time it became known for its speed and quality, and for a significant period it was the preferred bow for international competition.² The trophies that currently form part of the Du Plessis Collection, in turn, included the Bloemfontein Sherwood Bowmen Men’s Championship Trophy³,

Orange Free State Women’s Provincial Championship Rembrandt Trophy⁴, and the Orange Free State Archery Association Men’s Gold Cup Trophy – all associated with local and regional history.⁵ These items were all donated to the museum by the Du Plessis family, resident in the city in 2009 and who were recipients of the trophies at one time or another.

Henry du Plessis represented the Free State in inter-provincial archery and in addition to winning the provincial title, he also became the national or South African champion in 1965. This was followed by his winning national colours and being selected to represent South Africa in the World Championship Tournament in Sweden later that year. He was, coincidentally, also appointed as the Springbok captain for this tour. Under normal circumstances, this would have made him a strong contender for a place in the South African Olympic Games team for both the scheduled 1964 and 1968 Olympic Games. South Africa was, however, excluded from both because of its racial policies.

- 1 National Museum, Bloemfontein Collection (hereafter NMB) 19486, Ex 2/12 – J. du Plessis, De La Rey Avenue, Bloemfontein
- 2 Anon., *Harold Groves – Groves Spitfire Bows*, <http://www.vintagearchery.org/groves-archery.html> (accessed: 23.10.2023).
- 3 NMB 19485, Ex 2/12 - J. du Plessis, De La Rey Avenue, Bloemfontein.
- 4 NMB 19484, Ex 2/12 - J. du Plessis, De La Rey Avenue, Bloemfontein.
- 5 NMB 19483, Ex 2/14 - J. du Plessis, De La Rey Avenue, Bloemfontein.

Figure 1: Du Plessis suitcase 1: Groves Spitfire 42TH bow, competition photographs and trophies. (photo: Marelle van Rensburg)

Henry's wife, Anna, was an equally skilled archer and she won the Free State women's archery championship more than once. She also represented the Free State in 1963 together with her husband. Their son, Willie, followed in their footsteps and became South Africa's junior archery champion in 1968 and again in 1970. In addition to artefacts, the donation also includes several newspaper clippings and photographs (Fig. 2) and it tells the story of one family's close ties with archery as a national sport during the 1960s. Furthermore, it gives an idea of local activity's intersections with both national and international events and, therefore, served as a lens into South African archery's turbulent history.

The history of archery, in general, is a largely unmapped landscape that is neither mentioned in G.A.

Parker's *South African Sports* published in 1897 or H.P. Swaffer's similarly named study published in 1914.⁶ Furthermore, historians such as K.C. Donaldson claim that the sport in South Africa was at best an ad hoc activity before 1930, and that target archery was only formally introduced during the 1930s. It is further claimed that archery as a codified and formal sporting activity was only formally introduced in Cape Town, Durban and Johannesburg by 1946.⁷ These claims, however, do not align with the available historical records. Contemporary newspapers, for example, indicated that the sport was widely practised in the Cape Colony (and Natal to a lesser extent) during the 19th century. In addition, archery equipment was available for sale in all the South African colonies, including the Orange Free

6 See G.A. Parker, *South African Sports* (London: Low, Marston & Co., 1897), *passim*; H.P. Swaffer (ed.), *South African Sport* (Johannesburg: Transvaal Leader, 1914), *passim*.

7 K.C. (ed.) Donaldson, *The South African Sporting Encyclopaedia and Who's Who* (Johannesburg: Donaldson Publications, 1949), p. 9.

Figure 2: Du Plessis suitcase 2: Scrapbook and ticket. (photo: Marelle van Rensburg)

State, from as far back as the 1850s. Given this situation and the fact that archery forms an integral part of South Africa's national sports identity, its past needs to be retrieved and inserted into the historical mainstream.⁸

Against this background, this study uses a combination of official and newspaper archives as well as secondary literature to reconstruct the history of archery in both Bloemfontein and South Africa to use it as a lens to investigate the intersection of local and international sports events with, and the impact it had

on individual and collective lives. The Johannesburg-based *Rand Daily Mail* was extensively used since it, more than the Cape Town or Natal papers, covered both regional and provincial event results in great detail. The main Orange Free State papers lacked detail.

FROM INDIVIDUAL TO CLUB ACTIVITY DURING THE 19TH CENTURY

A survey of historical newspapers indicated that some of the earliest advertisements for the sale of

8 F. van der Merwe & F. Cleophas, Mapping out an obscured South African sport history landscape through Edward Henderson history, *African Journal for Physical Health Education, Recreation and Dance* 17(2), 2011, p. 233.

archery equipment appeared in the local media in Cape Town as far back as the 1850s. During August 1853, T.J. Hitchcock of Shortmarket Street in Cape Town notified the public of the impending arrival of a shipment of goods including archery, crossbows and arrows.⁹ This and other advertisements were subsequently repeated throughout the decade. This seems to suggest that the intended clients were individual enthusiasts that imported their sport into the Cape Colony. The first recorded club, the Cape Town Archery Club, was founded in the city in 1862. A key driver in this regard was Katherine Mary Templer, the wife of the Governor of the Cape Colony, Sir Philip Wodehouse. Several others, including the Sea Point (Cape Town, 1863) and the Grahamstown clubs (1864) were subsequently founded. With no local manufacturer, equipment was imported from England, which, in turn, made it possible to initiate a formal competition.¹⁰ Shortly thereafter several clubs, involving both sexes, were established throughout the Cape Colony in both the main urban centres, such as Grahamstown (1865), and key rural towns, such as Cradock and Graaff-Reinet, during the 1860s. The eastern districts clubs formally launched their competition in February 1872 at an occasion attended by the Cape Governor, Lord Barkly.¹¹ Over the next two decades growth continued to be strong in the Cape Peninsula with more clubs being added such as Wynberg (1890), Westbrooke (c. 1894), San Souci, and Suburban (1899).¹² Similarly, in the eastern districts of the Cape Colony, and thanks to the efforts of the Ancient Order of Foresters, a new club in Port Elizabeth joined the archery fraternity.¹³

Outside the Cape Colony the sport also found favour with enthusiasts in neighbouring Natal with reports of an active club existing in Pietermaritzburg (est. 1878). Testifying to the ever-growing popularity of the sport, reports started to appear of the possibility of the establishment of an archery club for black women in Natal.¹⁴ Unfortunately, no detail about the individuals or collective behind the initiative was

reported. Two years before the end of the 19th century, enthusiasts established the Durban Archery Club on 12 August.¹⁵ Although no club activity was reported in the Transvaal and Orange Free State republics, some evidence such as newspaper advertisements indicated the existence of archery enthusiasts that motivated local dealers to start importing equipment for sale. One such advertisement which appeared in *The Friend of the Free State and Bloemfontein Gazette* newspaper during 1881, offered archery equipment for sale in the Free State capital.¹⁶

The existing clubs were in most cases open to white members of colonial society of both sexes. Clubs such as the Cape Town-based Suburban Archery Club further drew its members exclusively from the ranks of the colonial bureaucrats employed by the colonial administration in Government House. It was, therefore, not surprising, judging by the regular media reports, that archery events were important and even lavish affairs that attracted a significant attendance. Some clubs, such as the Westbrooke Archery Club in Cape Town under the presidency of Reverend Canon George Ogilvie, a prominent individual in education, church and sporting circles, were active in running their own competitions, operated on a system of invited friends – suggesting a sense of exclusivity in operations.¹⁷ It was particularly the case in more distant areas such as in the rural parts of the eastern districts of the Cape Colony. Indeed, the *Eastern Province Herald* reported in December 1864 that the Cradock Ladies Archery Club had both a meeting and a very competitive contest, which they combined with an enjoyable tea.¹⁸ To emphasise its exclusivity and class character the Grahamstown club, for example, consistently held its club meetings, whether for the changing of club rules or ordinary business, on a Thursday afternoon at 15h00 – a time when most ordinary working-class enthusiasts were at work and unable to attend. Similarly, the *Transvaal Argus* reported that “private parties, concerts and theatricals, archery and croquet are, and have been

9 Anon., Hourly expected per 'Paramatta', *Mercantile Advertiser*, 6.8.1853, p. 8.

10 V. de Kock, *The fun they had: The pastimes of our forefathers* (Cape Town: Howard B. Timmins, 1955), pp. 158-159.

11 Anon., Marriage in high life, *Natal Witness*, 13.2.1872, p. 3.

12 See for example Anon., Archery club, *Cape Times*, 8.9.1890, p. 1; Anon., Archery, *Cape Times*, 25.4.1899, p. 7; Anon., San Souci Archery Society, *Cape Mercantile Advertiser*, 4.12.1867, p. 1; Anon., Archery club, *Cape Times*, 8.9.1890, p. 1.

13 Anon., Forrester's anniversary, *Eastern Province Herald*, 7.8.1895, p. 4.

14 Anon., Weekly Notes, *Port Elizabeth Telegraph*, 27.11.1883, p. 3.

15 Anon., An archery club, *Cape Times*, 13.8.1895, p. 5.

16 Anon., Important notice, *The Friend of the Free State and Bloemfontein Gazette*, 15.12.1881, p. 5.

17 Anon., Westbrooke Archery Club, *Cape Times*, 26.5.1894, p. 1.

18 Anon., Cradock, *Eastern Province Herald*, 13.12.1864, p. 3.

during the winter, all the rage”¹⁹ in the Graaff-Reinet district. Thus, when some females attended a ball of the local Graaff-Reinet Archery Club in simple ball dress, they were severely criticised for their poor taste of both dress and knowledge.²⁰ The *Cape Times* described one such archery gathering hosted in the Assembly Hall in Cape Town as a “numerous and fashionable assembly”.²¹

These trends and the prominence of the colonial higher middle-class and the local elite in archery affairs were not surprising and were consistent with practices overseas, where meetings of archery societies in both England and Wales were often characterised by the wearing of “outlandish costumes” and the hosting of “extravagant dinners”, and as opportunities for its female members and participants to show off their “feminine form” from the late 18th century well into the 19th century.²² An added attraction, arguably, was the close association of archery clubs in the colony with the British Royal Toxophilite Society, the control-body of the sport in the Mother Country, that had the British monarch as its patron.²³

The Anglo-Boer (South African) War (1899–1902) disrupted the first phase of local archery growth. Although some sporadic activity continued, no formal inter-colonial or inter-regional competitions were held because of martial law, lack of transport and the need for travel permits. This resulted in locals forfeiting an opportunity to participate in the first major event, namely the Paris Olympic Games. Archers in Cape Town, however, staged a fundraiser for the “Tommy’s Welcome to the Cape” campaign and contributed £2.1 to the fund as a demonstration of their loyalty to the British cause.²⁴

TOWARDS A NATIONAL SPORT, 1902–1949

During the war, the archery equipment remained an integral part of the products renowned sports goods

company, The Sports’ Depot, owned by Thurston & Co. of Greenmarket Square in Cape Town, offered for sale.²⁵ Their catalogue of goods was advertised in Cape, Rhodesian, and Mozambican newspapers throughout the period of conflict. This suggests that they had an established client-base interested in procuring the available products on offer. By the second half of 1901 and with the war starting to shift towards its final phase, some clubs such as Suburban in Cape Town that had succeeded in maintaining some activity, felt confident enough to start advertising for new members and to resume its normal activities.²⁶ By April and with the conflict nearing its end, competition was resumed at the Newlands Cricket Ground with 50 participants in attendance. Following the competition and awards ceremony, the gathering spent a “pleasant” day together.²⁷ By October 1902, with peace concluded, the club was actively busy hosting its domestic competition. Since it made use of the available cricket oval to host its events at an annual rent, it often had to reschedule their events so as not to interfere with the playing of cricket matches.

The period before the founding of the Union of South Africa (1910) was one of slow growth for the sport of archery. The most publicised and visible activity was largely Cape Town-based with little similar developments elsewhere. The available media reports indeed sketched a picture of fragmentation of a series of unlinked activity. Examples of these included a *Rand Daily Mail* feature on summer fashion, with a dress suitable for the “fair archer” that would not impede her prowess.²⁸ During the same period, St. Andrews, a new high school for girls in Parktown, Johannesburg, included facilities for archery in their layout and final building. The Transvaal media, like that of its Cape counterparts, however, continued to carry regular advertisements for archery equipment, which pointed to an ongoing interest in and of individual practice of the activity. The sport, in most cases, was often part of athletics events or social gatherings. In another positive

19 Anon., Monthly Notes from Graaff-Reinet”, *Transvaal Argus*, 4.9.1866, p. 3.

20 Anon., Graaff-Reinet Calico Ball, *Grahamstown Journal*, 9.10.1876, p. 2.

21 Anon., Local and General, *Eastern Province Herald*, 15.10.1867, p. 6.

22 M. Johnes, Archery, romance and elite culture in England and Wales, c. 1780–1840, *History* 89(294), 2004, pp. 193-208.

23 M. Huggins, Sport and the British upper classes c. 1500–2000: A historiographic overview, *Sport in History* 28(3), 2008, pp. 364-388.

24 Anon., Tommy’s welcome to the Cape, *Cape Times*, 2.2.1900, p. 5.

25 Anon., Thurston & Co., *Rand Daily Mail*, 13.1.1900, p. 4.

26 Anon., Suburban Archery Club, *Cape Times*, 19.9.1901, p. 4.

27 Anon., News of the Day, *Cape Times*, 14.4.1902, p. 5.

28 Anon., The latest holiday fashions, *Rand Daily Mail*, 6.8.1904, p. 13.

development the existence of an archery club in Pretoria was reported in the *Cape Daily Telegraph* in 1905.²⁹

The period after Unification was also characterised by slow growth of organised interclub and interprovincial archery. Individual practice thereof, however, continued as evidenced by the constant advertising of bows and arrows as individual items or as toys in the mainstream media. It also made an appearance in both insolvent and deceased estates and its associated auctions. In addition, local newspapers continued to publish reports about various overseas archery events, including the World Archery Championships and the Olympic Games. This helped to keep the sport in the public mind in the absence of organised competitions involving clubs and associations. In June 1914, the sport was also readmitted into the Olympic Games. Impeding factors were the start and duration of the First World War (1914–1918), the challenges of post-war reconstruction and the Great Flu (1918), and by 1929, the start of the Great Depression. Under these conditions, South Africa remained an interested observer of the international unfolding of the sport at events such as the Olympic Games.

The decade before the start of the Second World War (1939–1945) was equally characterised by slow growth. Archery, however, made a regular appearance as part of a comprehensive programme of entertainment. At the beginning of the 1930s, it was common to see it listed as part of the programme of venues and institutions such as the Moulin Rouge Co. “entertainment providers” in Johannesburg. Similarly, a golf course development in the Orange Free State town of Virginia, as part of its marketing campaign, advertised archery as a future offering beyond its normal programme.³⁰ The *Rand Daily Mail* further gave ample space to the coverage of the 1933 World Archery Championship at Ranelagh Club in the UK, where eight nations participated for the three-year-old title with the USA, France and Belgium as the favourites.³¹

Beyond the activities within the white community, the sport also received a timeous boost from the local Indian populace and the occasional tours of visiting Indian performers such as a group from the Baroda State, who had included archery as an integral part of their performance. During 1910, the Indian Athletic Association Troupe in Durban presented what was billed as “a sensational feats of archery and athletics” at the Electric Theatre.³² Archery was further combined with a display of dagger and knife throwing to entertain paying clients. During 1934, the visiting Indian Girl Guides staged various displays, including archery, before mixed audiences during their three month tour of the Union.³³ They performed, inter alia, at events at the Baragwanath Aerodrome in Johannesburg,³⁴ the Masonic Hall in Krugersdorp and at the Johannesburg City Hall.³⁵ In addition, the feats of the travelling Indian entertainer, under the stage name “Professor Yashpal”, hosted by the Transvaal United Patidar Society, Transvaal Hindu Educational Council and Young Men Hindu Association collectively, received wide publicity. During his a month-long tour of the Union of South Africa in 1937, he performed in front of mixed audiences of whites and people of colour at venues such as the Inchcape Hall in Johannesburg and Durban.³⁶ His performance included various feats involving a variety of archery tricks, which were presented as part of the “ancient arts of India” and in which he demonstrated “astonishing mastery”.³⁷ This was augmented by reports the following year of the involvement of three South Africans on the movie set of the film *Robin Hood*, in which Errol Flynn played the leading role.³⁸

In the first year of the Second World War, and concomitant with the 1939 World Archery Championships held in Paris, France, the first recorded club in Transvaal was established. Named the Adventurer’s Archery Club, it was founded in Johannesburg by Captain Wally Vane-Wallace. The club had a mixed

29 Anon., Pretoria News, *Cape Daily Telegraph*, 28.3.1905, p. 5.

30 Anon., Moulin Rouge, *Rand Daily Mail*, 12.12.1931, p. 9. See also Anon., Northcliff Weekend Recreation Club, *Rand Daily Mail*, 11.10.1939, p. 8.

31 Anon., Revival of archery, *Rand Daily Mail*, 2.8.1933, p. 11.

32 Anon., Electric Theatre, *Indian Opinion*, 1.1.1910, p. 23.

33 Anon., Indian girls are expert with ..., *Rand Daily Mail*, 15.8.1934, p. 11.

34 Anon., Flip for Indian Girl Guides, *Rand Daily Mail*, 28.8.1934, p. 14.

35 Anon., Indian Girl Guides Display, *Rand Daily Mail*, 27.8.1934, p. 7.

36 Anon., At the Inchcape Hall, *Bantu World*, 4.9.1937, p. 5.

37 Anon., Professor Yashpal, *Rand Daily Mail*, 25.8.1937, p. 11; Anon., Indian stops his pulse and lives: Yogi’s great feats, *Rand Daily Mail*, 25.8.1937, p. 13.

38 Anon., Three South Africans in ‘Robin Hood’, *Rand Daily Mail*, 10.1.1938, p. 7.

membership (men and women) and committed itself to work towards the establishment of a Transvaal Association. To overcome problems with acquiring bows and arrows, it resorted to manufacturing its own equipment. In the absence of proper facilities, it used the open spaces in Irene and Kenilworth for practices and competitions.³⁹ The Adventurers were soon after joined by the Robin Hoods Archery Club which it immediately engaged in competition.⁴⁰ This effectively established an organised archery presence in three of the four provinces of the Union of South Africa. As the war got underway, the Orange Free State was the only area without a known club presence.

During the war, domestic archery activity remained low, and its growth was in fact severely constrained. Right at the start of the war in September 1939, the Inanda Club in Durban hosted a “war gymkhana”, inclusive of archery as part of the “sideshow” to raise funds for the Mayor’s Food Fund.⁴¹ Thereafter the sport, like its other counterparts, effectively disappeared from the news for the rest of the conflict. Already struggling to make the transition towards a fully-fledged local activity, this decline made its revival so much more difficult. Following the conclusion of the war, archery enthusiasts in Cape Town, Durban and Johannesburg started to revive the sport. Notable personalities in this regard were individuals such as former Pole and world champion Irena Shorupska, Alfred Sewell and Sam Hikins, respectively.⁴² One of the first new clubs to be founded in the Transvaal in the immediate post-war period was the Brakpan Archery Club in 1947. They received general assistance from the long-established Morena Club when the former hosted their “sports tableau”.⁴³ On a regular basis Morena presented what was called “daring archery exhibitions” in the city – a development that contributed to the further revival of the sport. Other initiatives included the hosting of innovative events such as an “archery tea gardens” to awaken public interest.⁴⁴

A year later, with the number of Witwatersrand clubs having increased to six, the Pretoria club hosted the first

Transvaal Archery Championship Tournament in June 1948 at Loftus Versfeld in the city.⁴⁵ The participating clubs, which also became the founding members of the Transvaal Archery Association on the occasion, were Morena, Brakpan, Louis Trichardt, Poison Arrow, Pretoria, and Krugersdorp, plus a number of individual players from Nelspruit (Mbombela). At this point, the number of archery clubs nationally stood at 25 individual and active bodies spread over the different provinces and steadily became more representative of a growing working-class and semi-rural membership base. This laid the foundation for the founding of a national body, the South African Toxophilite Society, established under the leadership of Matt Sluyter, consisting of Transvaal, Western Province and Natal, later that year. The only remaining entity was the Orange Free State, the fourth province of the Union of South Africa. Without avail, the new body affiliated to the Federation International de Tir a l’Arch (FITA), which would allow the country participation in key events such as the world championships, Empire Games and Olympic Games.⁴⁶

ARCHERY FROM APARTHEID TO SHARPEVILLE, 1950–1960

Following its electoral victory in 1948, the Reunited National Party of South Africa (Herengigde Nasionale Party; HNP), who campaigned the general election on a political platform that promised white voters institutionalized segregation, started to promulgate various laws to achieve its objectives. Amongst the legislated measures were the *Prohibition of Mixed Marriages Act* (Act no. 55 of 1949), the *Population Registration Act* (Act no. 30 of 1950), the *Group Areas Act* (Act no. 41 of 1951), the *Separate Representation of Voters Act* (Act no. 46 of 1951), the *Reservation of Separate Amenities Act* (Act no. 49 of 1953), and the *Native Laws Amendment Act* (Act no. 54 of 1952). The stipulations of the *Population Registration Act*, which had for the purposes of governance, subdivided the South African population along racial lines, was, according to Keith Breckenridge, “the bureaucratic

39 R.M. Graham, Archery came to the Transvaal, *Rand Daily Mail*, 17.5.1939, p. 3.

40 Anon., Archery at Irene, *Rand Daily Mail*, 15.5.1939, p. 16.

41 Anon., Vanity Fair, *Rand Daily Mail*, 28.9.1939, p. 9.

42 S. Hikins, Archery, in K.C. Donaldson (ed.), *The South African Sporting Encyclopaedia and Who’s Who* (Johannesburg: Donaldson Publications, 1949), p. 9.

43 Anon., Brakpan sports tableau, *Rand Daily Mail*, 30.1.1948, p. 13.

44 Anon., Miscellaneous – Archery Tea Gardens, *Rand Daily Mail*, 4.10.1946, p. 2.

45 Anon., True as an arrow’s flight, *Rand Daily Mail*, 28.6.1948, p. 7.

46 M. Eorwine, Archery – ‘Field takes off’, in B. Deans (ed.), *Allied Book of South African Sport and Sports Records, 1988–89* (Randburg: SASBOR, 1989), p. 18.

cornerstone of the apartheid state, the lynch-pin of the Group Areas Act".⁴⁷ Collectively, this suite of legislation outlawed inter-racial marriages and sexual relations, provided for separate residential areas, prohibited racial social mixing in most areas of life, and removed blacks from the common voters roll.

The apartheid authorities further used the *Suppression of Communism Act* (Act no. 44 of 1950) to repress any resistance against their policies. Although there was no specific legislation passed to formalise segregated sport, black athletes continued to be excluded from national teams. The *Reservation of Separate Amenities Act* (Act no. 49 of 1953) left black communities with minimal facilities. Archery, still in the process of developing a national profile, therefore, entered its new era, like all other sports, as a racially exclusive activity. By 1952, with the celebration of the Van Riebeeck Sports Festival, an event aimed at celebrating the tercentenary of the landing of the Dutch colonists under Jan van Riebeeck (1652), archery became further enmeshed in the politics of apartheid. On the occasion which was boycotted by the black community, Polish and Western Province champion and South African resident Irene Shorupska, competed in an archery contest with two "Bushmen" at the Festival Fair in Cape Town during April 1952.⁴⁸ Beyond the festival, the South African Airforce Association offered archery as part of their morning market fundraising activities while the South African National Championship, as decided in Colesberg previously, took place in Durban.⁴⁹

In 1953, the practice of archery in Bloemfontein, specifically the activities of the local Sherwood Bowmen Archery Club, formally came to the national attention. It boasted amongst the club membership, esteemed individuals such as Appeal Court Judge Van den Heever, a fact that attracted the attention of the Johannesburg-based newspaper, the *Rand Daily Mail*.⁵⁰ Furthermore, the club made news during August when its two members, Bill Grant and Bob Attree, set a new South African record of striking a target at 320 yards with the 60 pounds bow, thrice in one week. The new record was, however, not

recognised since it was set during a local rather than an interprovincial event, thus unofficial.⁵¹ This feat was significant enough for others in the archery fraternity to take note of. During its inaugural year, the Sherwood Bowmen Club further introduced its Championship Trophy for the Bloemfontein Archery Championship, which was donated by Kurt Schmidt, a local businessman. The first recipients of the floating trophy, which was competed for in November, were a married couple, Jan and Lal Jacobs, who won the male and female sections respectively. The runners up were Bill Grand and Eric Prince.⁵² Thereafter, this trophy was continuously awarded until 1965.

Following its entry into competitive archery, Bloemfontein hosted its first South African championships a year later. Attended by several clubs from across the country, competitions provided for several categories, including long and short distance, national flight shoot, inter-club and provincial title. Testifying to its undoubted depth amongst its archers, the local club finished in the second position in the Provincial Shoot, after Iscor. This set the stage for overall improvement at the next year's championship held at the Iscor Club in Pretoria. On this occasion, R. Botha of Bloemfontein won the Women's Short Distance. Furthermore, the Bloemfontein Club finished in second place in the interclub category, while the Free State finished second in the interprovincial category. To top it off, Eric Prince finished second in the Men's Short Distance category.⁵³

The 1955 season saw the number of registered archery clubs country-wide rapidly increasing to 750 registered individual archers. This development coincided with the sport being included in the Witwatersrand University's Town's Festival, which provided the activity with much-needed additional advertising. Continuing the same growth trajectory, the Bloemfontein archers yet again participated in the national championship held in Benoni in June. They returned from this event with members B. Els having won the Junior Championship and A. de Beer the National Flight Shoot. In addition, S. Botha (Bloemfontein) finished second in the men's division

47 K. Breckenridge, *The Book of Life: The South African population register and the invention of racial descent, 1950–1980*, *Kronos* 40(1), 2014, p. 225.

48 Anon., Archers three, *Rand Daily Mail*, 7.4.1952, p. 10.

49 Anon., Colesberg, *Rand Daily Mail*, 6.11.1951, p. 12.

50 Anon., Flying Judge sells plane, buys bicycle, *Rand Daily Mail*, 4.11.1953, p. 11.

51 Anon., Archery record is unofficial, *Rand Daily Mail*, 6.8.1953, p. 12.

52 Anon., Man and wife win archery contest, *Rand Daily Mail*, 3.11.1953, p. 6.

53 Anon., Archery S.A. Championship, *Rand Daily Mail*, 11.4.1955, p. 4.

after Ronnie Hunter, the South African Champion. His team mate R. Botha (Bloemfontein), in turn, became the new women's national champion. They concluded the year with four local archers, D.S. Botha, Jan Jacobs, C. Breytenbach and Eric Prince scoring more than 800 points in a single competition for a South African record.⁵⁴ This season further saw Ronnie Hunter of Pretoria becoming the country's first national representative or "Springbok" at the World Championships in Finland where he finished in the 10th position.

Following their successful performances in the preceding national tournament, the Bloemfontein archery fraternity met the new season with increased confidence. They duly entered the field in April 1956 at Pietermaritzburg and returned from there with two finalists amongst the top male players. Members D.S. Botha and C. Breytenbach finished in second and fifth place, respectively.⁵⁵ This was followed by the Free State archers entering the Transvaal Championships at Vanderbijl Park. The local clubs, especially Iscor, however, proved to be too strong which resulted in the visitors returning to Bloemfontein without any honours.⁵⁶ This season also witnessed the Orange Free State Archery Association inaugurated the Men's Gold Cup Competition. The competition trophy was presented by Maitland Jewellers of Bloemfontein and C. Breytenbach became its first recipient. This floating trophy, based on the engraved information on the artefact's body, was likewise continuously awarded until 1972.

The 1957 season was another notable year in South African archery history. In continuing to expand the country's profile overseas, Bill White of the Zoo Lake Morena Archery Club in Johannesburg, represented South Africa at the World Archery Championship and World Archery Congress in Prague, Czechoslovakia, in July. He was, however, not awarded Springbok colours because of not having won the national title. The rationale behind his selection was merely coincidental with the archery authorities exploiting White's travelling to Europe in

his private capacity to stake a claim for itself as a sporting country of note. Furthermore, the position was that national colours would be awarded once he had achieved "Springbok standards", i.e. beating opponents during the world competition.⁵⁷ On the local front, the April South African Championship, which was held in Emmerentia, Johannesburg, saw B. Duncan (Bloemfontein Sherwood Club) achieving second place in the South African Junior Beginners Championship, while N. Duncan also made an impression in the same division.⁵⁸ In another boost for Free State archery, 18 July 1957 saw the establishment of the Virginia Archery Club with 20 members. This was preceded by an event of even greater significance, namely the first recorded incidence of training in archery of disabled people at the Avalon Centre for Disabled in Johannesburg.⁵⁹

In April 1958, the national championships returned to the Free State capital. Contrary to expectations, none of the local archers won any prizes.⁶⁰ In the men's section, Mervin Hurst (Iscor) dominated proceedings and walked away with the championship title. The disappointment and lack of honours for the hosts was, however, mitigated when three Bloemfontein archers, namely Jannie and Lal Jacobs as well as Mrs Van der Berg, were included in the 11-member national team to represent South Africa at the world championships in Belgium.⁶¹ The year 1959 saw the inauguration of the Orange Free State Provincial Women's Championship Trophy. This competition's floating trophy was donated by Rembrandt Furnishers in Bloemfontein. As was the case with the Sherwood Bowmen's Trophy, and based on the engravings on the artefact, the winner and first recipient were Lal Jacobs, one of the most experienced archers in the local circuit. On the national front, the prospects for the sport improved significantly with discussions about South Africa's possible entry into the Stoke-Mandeville Games in England for the disabled the following year, in addition to further participation in the world championships scheduled for Oslo, Norway, in 1961. The national interprovincial championship, in turn, took place in Durban.⁶²

54 Anon., Archery record, *Rand Daily Mail*, 17.11.1955, p. 16.

55 Anon., Hunter's 3rd title in a row, *Rand Daily Mail*, 2.4.1956, p. 13.

56 Anon., Archer sends arrow 433 yds: S.A. record, *Rand Daily Mail*, 5.6.1956, p. 9.

57 Anon., Archer for World Championships, *Rand Daily Mail*, 11.6.1957, p. 10.

58 Anon., National Archery Results, *Rand Daily Mail*, 23.4.1957, p. 4.

59 Anon., Sister Iris takes a bow, *Rand Daily Mail*, 11.5.1957, p. 3.

60 Anon., Hurst retain archery title, *Rand Daily Mail*, 7.4.1958, p. 12.

61 Anon., Archers choose 11 for Brussels, *Rand Daily Mail*, 9.4.1958, p. 16.

62 Anon., Rest of sport in brief, *Rand Daily Mail*, 31.3.1959, p. 15.

FROM SHARPEVILLE TO INTERNATIONAL EXCLUSION, 1960–1970

On the 21 March 1960, South Africa exploded in an orgy of violence following the police killing of 69 demonstrators at Sharpeville on the Witwatersrand following an anti-pass march aimed at forcing the abolition of restrictions on the freedom of movement of blacks. In its wake, several so-called “backlash demonstrations” were organised by various political organisations.⁶³ As the unrest spread across the country, the apartheid regime banned several political organisations, including the African National Congress (ANC) and Pan Africanist Congress (PAC) under the *Unlawful Organisations Act* (Act no. 34 of 1960). Utilising the protection and cover of a declared state of emergency, the law enforcement agencies further used all the means at their disposal to repress opponents of the system and detained, killed, or exiled scores of activists.⁶⁴

Following the Sharpeville events, the *American Committee on Africa* (ACOA) started a *South Africa Emergency Campaign* and issued a “Call to Action” imploring ordinary Americans to join the worldwide boycott of South Africa. It further protested South Africa’s scheduled participation in the Olympic Games in Rome during the same period.⁶⁵ In addition, Dr Martin Luther King Jr. and Oliver Tambo (president of the exiled ANC), issued a joint “Appeal for Action Against Apartheid” (AAAA). This call was soon taken up by anti-apartheid activists and solidarity organisations on both sides of the Atlantic, who started to organise a diverse range of sector-specific movements. One of the first responders was the Campaign Against Race Discrimination in Sport (CARDIS) established by, among others, Father Trevor Huddleston, an Anglican priest and apartheid critic, one year before the Sharpeville shootings. From the onset, the CARDIS strived to end all whites-

only sports tours and it was one of the first to call for the total isolation of the apartheid state and was thus supportive of the call for a cultural boycott.⁶⁶

The first cultural boycott against apartheid South Africa in the “search for a much larger, multi-textured effort to achieve far-reaching alterations” was initiated by the *British Musicians Union* (BMU) during 1961, whose members refused to perform before segregated audiences. Additionally, they refused performance rights to South African theatres, which practiced racial segregation and discriminated on the basis of race. The effectiveness of this campaign was strengthened when members of the *British Screenwriters Guild*, *British Equity*, *American Equity*, as well as individual British, Irish and American playwrights joined the boycott during the decade.⁶⁷ This notwithstanding, South Africa participated in the World Championships in Oslo. The team, led by Bloemfontein archer, Jannie Jacobs, performed commendably and the South African women’s team finished in third position, after the USA and England.⁶⁸ On the home front, Welkom hosted the national championships.

As the campaign to exclude South Africa from international participation intensified during the next season, the national body started to prepare for participation in the Wheelchair Games and Empire Games, which were both scheduled to be hosted by Australia. The national championship, in turn, was set for Paarl during the Easter weekend. The Free State Archery Championships, on the other hand, were held in Virginia and won by two members of the local Harmony Archery Club in May 1962.⁶⁹ On the international front, the national team captured the gold medal at the Stoke-Mandeville Games in July 1962.⁷⁰

In 1963, Henry du Plessis was awarded Free State provincial colours for archery. He soon became the

63 R.A. Francisco, The dictator’s dilemma, in C. Davenport, H. Johnston & C. Mueller (eds), *Repression and mobilization* 64(2) (Minneapolis/London: University of Minnesota Press, 2005), p. 71.

64 K.A. O’Brien, Counter-intelligence for counter-revolutionary warfare: The South African police security branch 1979–1990, *Intelligence and National Security*, 16(3), 2001, p. 29.

65 American Committee on Africa (ACOA), *South Africa Emergency Campaign: A Call to Action, April 1960*. Available from African Activist Archives, Michigan State University (<https://www.africanactivist.msu.edu>), no p. no.

66 T. Huddleston, *Naught for your comfort* (Glasgow: Collins, 1956), p. 150.

67 E.S. Reddy, Cultural boycott: Statement by Director of U.N. Centre Against Apartheid: Press briefing. Available from <https://bdsmovement.net/news/cultural-boycott-statement-enuga-s-reddy-director-un-centre-against-apartheid-press-briefing> (accessed: 1.3.2019), no p. no.

68 Anon., S.A. placings in archery events, *Rand Daily Mail*, 15.8.1961, p. 18.

69 Anon., Virginia, *Rand Daily Mail*, 14.5.1962, p. 18.

70 Anon., Paralysed Springboks cheered! *Rand Daily Mail*, 30.7.1962, p. 2.

provincial archery champion and by 1965 he won the national championship. Henry was included in the national team to compete in the World Championship Tournament in Sweden in July 1965. He was, coincidentally, also the Springbok captain for this tour. Under normal circumstances, this would have made him a strong contender for a place in the South African Olympic Games team for both the scheduled 1964 and 1968 Olympic Games in Japan and Mexico. The country was, however, excluded from both because of its racial policies. This, nonetheless, did not dampen the enthusiasm, motivation and competitiveness of the Du Plessis family judged by their continued participation in competitive archery based on the trophy engravings.

Henry's wife, Anna, was an equally skilled archer in her own right and won the Free State women's archery championship more than once. She also represented Free State in 1963 together with her husband. Their son, Willie, followed in his parents' footsteps and became South Africa's junior archery champion in 1968 and again in 1970. This period, however, saw the demise of the Bloemfontein Sherwood Bowmen Championship Trophy Competition. In addition, in December 1968, the United Nations General Assembly adopted Resolution 2396 that called upon member states and associated organisations to suspend all cultural, educational, sports and other exchanges with the apartheid government, its organisations and institutions.⁷¹

Although some South African sports teams such as the national rugby team were still able to tour overseas during late 1969 and 1970, this was confronted by mass protests in the United Kingdom and Ireland. At the head of these protests were the anti-apartheid group *Stop All Racist Tours* (SART) led by Peter Hain, an exiled South African supported by several trade unions. Within this context, John Lennon of the *Beatles*, confidentially assisted with the payment of the fines of several arrested protestors.⁷² Whether the earlier banning of the music of the *Beatles* in South Africa played a role in this decision is, however, not clear. In 1970, several South African sports

bodies lost their international affiliation and were cut off from any further international participation. Given this collective pressure, South Africa was not only expelled from the International Olympic Committee but also from several other world sports bodies between 1964 and post-1970. These events are indelibly etched into the history of South Africa's sporting history.

Facing an uncertain future, some South African sports federations demanded action from the Department of Sport and Recreation, who, with due consideration to its central constituency, chose to reiterate the government's opposition to any form of racial mixing. It further rejected all external pressure for change and insisted that South Africa alone would decide who to invite and play against. This inflexibility generated increasingly violent opposition to all-white South African teams at international events, forcing them to consider some changes of a political nature. However, it came too late for the likes of the Du Plessis family. Although South Africa, thanks to its Western allies, maintained its membership and continued to enjoy a modicum of international competition, its national archery association had to do so as an unrepresented field archery association and not as a body representative of a nation.⁷³ Therefore, its athletes became the true victims of the reluctance of politicians to move beyond their vested interests, a situation that remained until 1991 and the start of South Africa's political transition.

ASSESSMENT

Based on the aforementioned events, South Africa in general, and Bloemfontein in particular, have a rich and multi-layered archery history that is not always appreciated. In this era of mass media and the dominance of sports like rugby, soccer and cricket, individual sports on the margins continued to be overlooked despite their contribution to the country's national sporting identity. The current research is aimed at contributing to foreground one such sport with a view to aiding the writing of a more comprehensive history. Furthermore, the

71 United Nations, *The United Nations and Apartheid, 1948–1994* (New York: Department of Public Information, United Nations, 1994), p. 356.

72 Anon., Government's 30-year-old files reveal ugly side of Springboks tour that brought shame on our nation: Day John Lennon paid my demo fine, *Herald* (Scotland), 1 January 2001. Available from <https://www.heraldsotland.com/news/12157956.governments-30-year-old-files-reveal-ugly-side-of-springboks-tour-that-brought-shame-on-our-nation-day-john-lennon-paid-my-demo-fine> (accessed: 5.4.2018), no p. no.

73 Anon., SA wins 3 medals at great world shoot, *Rand Daily Mail*, 24.8.1984, p. 5.

aforementioned events conclusively proved that artefacts are indeed storied “probe objects”⁷⁴ that contain “much about a nation’s sporting culture and the social, economic, and political milieu in which it developed”.⁷⁵ The life and collections of artefacts

associated with individual athletes, their clubs and associations, are therefore a useful lens for the investigation of a range of wider issues, including questions such as class, nationhood, ethnicity, race, sexuality and gender.⁷⁶

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- 74 S. Benford, A. Hazzard, A. Chamberlain, K. Glover, C. Greenhalgh, L. Xu, M. Hoare & D. Darzentas, *Accountable Artefacts, Proceedings of the 2016 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems - CHI '16* (New York: ACM Press, 2016), no p. no.
- 75 W. Vamplew, Facts and artefacts: Sports historians and sports museums, *Journal of Sport History* 25(2), 1998, p. 268.
- 76 D. Allen, 'National heroes': Sport and the creation of icons, *Sport in History* 33(4), 2013, p. 584.